

Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESOO

Residential Buildings in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

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Abstract

The purpose of air conditioning systems is to lower the air's Heat Index (HI) from an uncomfortable level to a comfort level of temperature and humidity. Heat Index is the “feel like” air temperature that combines the actual temperature and humidity.

The publication “*Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*” [6] defined the comfort level of the Heat Index as a Comfort Heat Index (CHI) equal to 26.6°C (79.9°F).

The publication [6] also introduced the Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), a thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

The current work adds a minimum OCAC, MinOCAC = 25.35°C (77.63°F), the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort (CHI=26.6°C) even at 100% relative humidity.

Cooling below the Comfort Heat Index not only wastes energy but also causes serious discomfort and health hazards to many people. In this work, Heat Index above or below the Comfort Heat Index is considered equally uncomfortable conditions.

This work introduces two new terms related to air conditioning overcooling: Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) and Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning (OverAC).

OCHI is the difference between the Comfort Heat Index and the actual Heat Index, and OverAC is the product of OCHI and the extended time it lasts. For example, if the operation of air conditioning system results in a Heat Index 2°C below the CHI on average, and 1,000 hours more than CHI, the OCHI index will be 2°C and the OverAC index will be the product of 2°C per 1,000 hours, 2,000 degree-hours (dhr).

Running the BESOO simulation program for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv shows that setting the air conditioning thermostat to 16°C results in an OverAC index for Jerusalem of 51,434 dhr and for Tel Aviv of 45,265 dhr.

The BESOO Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization programs, used in this work, are available at:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Glossary

ΔE	overcooling air conditioning energy consumption for cooling and condense above baseline CHI, kWh thermal/year
$\Delta E\%$	overcooling energy, the ratio of actual energy consumption to baseline in CHI and OCAC, %
Δhr	overcooling hours, difference between actual cooling hours and comfort hours' baseline in CHI and OCAC, hr/y
$\Delta hr\%$	overcooling hours, the ratio of actual cooling hours to comfort hours' baseline in CHI and OCAC, %
Ave	average
AveHICdn	average Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours, °C
BL	baseline (for calculation of OverAC)
CHI	Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C
Cool On	thermostat setting of air conditioning, °C
dhr	degree-hours, unit of OverAC
ECW	thermal energy for cooling and condense, kWh th/y
HI	Heat Index – air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent, °C
HIC	Heat Index during cooling hours, °C
hrC	actual cooling hours, hr/y
hrCHI	cooling hours at CHI level, hr/y
MinOCAC	minimum OCAC = 25.35°C (77.63°F), the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort (CHI=26.6°C) at 100% relative humidity
OCAC	Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).
OCHI	Overcooling Heat Index - difference between the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and the actual Heat Index, °C

OverAC	Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning, multiplication of OCHI by operation hours below CHI (Δhr), dhr (degree-hours)
RH	relative humidity of air, %

Energy Units

Generally, this work is in metric units. Energy is expressed in Joule and power in Watts. Calculations and application of Heat Index involve degrees Fahrenheit. Time is GMT+2 for the whole year, DST is not considered.

Ambient Air Temperature, Relative Humidity and Solar Radiation Datasets

Ambient air temperature, air relative humidity (RH) and solar global radiation datasets for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv are from the Israel Meteorological Service [3]. The records are every 10 minutes. The datasets are for the years 2023 and 2024. Global solar radiation is multiplied by conversion factors according to the direction of the outside wall, the month and the hour. The conversion factor is from the website "*Global Solar Radiation in Tel Aviv, Typical Year, Monthly Averages, hourly data*" [4].

To avoid long period of stabilization of the simulation results (depending on the Thermal Time Constant – TTC of the building), the simulation starts on the coldest day of 2023. On the first day of the simulation the ambient air temperature is set to the first day's average until the same actual ambient temperature.

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Program - BESOO

The current version (544) is based on the publication “*Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO v512 - Thermal Energy for Space Heating, Air Conditioning and Removal of Humidity in Residential Buildings in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv*” [5].

The previous versions of BESOO are dedicated to space heating and air conditioning. The dataset starts in spring 2023, and the cooling is limited to the end of 2023. The current version (544) is dedicated to cooling only, and the cooling is not limited in time.

The default ventilation in this simulation program is 7 changes per hour.

The integration interval is 10 seconds.

The Building and the Apartment

The calculations are for the entire apartment and not for individual rooms; the entire apartment is considered one room.

It is assumed that the room temperature in all neighboring apartments is the same as in the tested apartment.

Chart 1 - Building and apartment

Heat Index – Air Humidity Temperature Equivalent

The Heat Index (HI) is the air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent, °C (or °F).

Following is the official definition of the Heat Index as on the NOAA site [1]:

“Heat Index

The Heat Index is a measure of how hot it really feels when relative humidity is factored in with the actual air temperature. To find the Heat Index temperature, look at the Heat Index Chart above or check our Heat Index Calculator. As an example, if the air temperature is 96°F and the relative humidity is 65%, the heat index--how hot it feels--is 121°F. The red area without numbers indicates extreme danger.

Since heat index values were devised for shady, light wind conditions, exposure to full sunshine can increase heat index values by up to 15°F. Also, strong winds, particularly with very hot, dry air, can be extremely hazardous.”

The Heat Index formula is described in detail in the publication “Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units” [6] based on NOAA equation [2].

Heat Index (HI) is calculated by “Nowagreen Heat Index and Overcooling Heat Index online calculator °C and °F “ [8] [9] on site:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/Hi>

and by “Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization – BESOO v544 - Comfort Heat Index, cooling only, thermostatic control, outside walls layers temperature, infiltration, ventilation, thermal energy for cooling and condense” [7] on sites:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Comfort Heat Index

Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is the Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling. Setting air conditioning systems to a Comfort Heat Index (CHI) provides air conditioning that is comfortable enough for those suffering from heat and much better for those suffering from air conditioning overcooling.

Cooling below the Comfort Heat Index not only wastes energy but also causes discomfort and health hazards for many people.

Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is described in detail in the publication “*Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*” [6].

Table 1 - Air Conditioning Comfort Heat Index (CHI) [6]

Air Conditioning Comfort Heat Index (CHI), °F	79.9
Air Conditioning Comfort Heat Index (CHI), °C	26.6

Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC)

Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC) refers to the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

Based on the analyzed data for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, the Heat Index remained below the Comfort Heat Index at cooling setpoint below 25.5°C in Jerusalem and 25.7°C in Tel Aviv.

This issue is described in detail in the publication [6].

Table 2 - Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), °C [6]

OCAC for Jerusalem, °C	25.4
OCAC for Tel Aviv, °C	25.6

Minimum Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (MinOCAC)

Extreme humidity does not require a significant lowering of the air conditioning thermostat to the typical 20°C -16°C, as demonstrated in the following table.

Table 3 - Comfort Heat Index at high humidity

RH	temp °C	temp °F	HI °C	HI °F
100%	25.35	77.63	26.50	79.69
100%	25.00	77.00	26.17	79.10
95%	25.50	77.90	26.59	79.86
90%	25.60	77.90	26.57	79.82
85%	25.75	78.35	26.60	79.88
80%	25.85	78.53	26.58	79.84
75%	25.95	78.71	26.56	79.81
70%	26.10	78.98	26.59	79.87
65%	26.20	79.16	26.57	79.83
60%	26.30	79.34	26.55	79.79
55%	26.45	79.61	26.59	79.86
50%	26.55	79.79	26.57	79.82

Even with 100% relative humidity, setting the thermostat to 25.35°C (77.63°F) ALWAYS results in a Heat Index below the comfort limit.

Minimum Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (MinOCAC) is when the relative humidity (RH) is 100% and the Heat Index is below the Comfort Heat Index of 26.6°C (79.9°F)

Table 4 - Minimum OCAC (MinOCAC) at 100% humidity

MinOCAC at 100% humidity, °C	25.35
MinOCAC at 100% humidity, °F	77.63

Overcooling Heat Index, OCHI

Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) is the difference between the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and the actual Heat Index (HI).

Formula 1 - Overcooling Heat Index, OCHI, °C

$$OCHI = CHI - HI$$

OCHI	Overcooling Heat Index, OCHI, °C
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, °C
HI	Heat Index, °C

Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI) is calculated by “*Nowagreen Heat Index and Overcooling Heat Index online calculator °C and °F* “ [8] [9] on site:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/Hi>

and by “*Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization – BESOO v544 – “Comfort Heat Index, cooling only, thermostatic control, outside walls layers temperature, infiltration, ventilation, thermal energy for cooling and condense”* [7] on sites:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Overcooling Heat Index, Energy, and Cooling Hours

Table 5 - Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), energy consumption (ECW), and cooling hours (hrC) - Jerusalem

Cool On °C	AveHICdn °C	OCHI °C	ECW kWh	ΔE%	hrC hr/y	Δhr%
16	15.06	11.54	8,004	871%	5,473	439%
17	16.16	10.44	7,270	782%	5,081	400%
18	17.24	9.36	6,495	688%	4,689	362%
19	18.32	8.28	5,697	591%	4,256	319%
20	19.38	7.22	4,823	485%	3,800	274%
21	20.42	6.18	3,818	363%	3,276	222%
22	21.46	5.14	2,884	250%	2,702	166%
23	22.51	4.09	2,108	156%	2,124	109%
24	23.56	3.04	1,482	80%	1,632	61%
25	24.61	1.99	990	20%	1,178	16%
OCAC						
25.4	25.02	1.58	824	0%	1,016	0%
Baseline	26.60	0.00	824		1,016	

Cool On	thermostat setting of air conditioning, °C
AveHICdn	average Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours, °C
OCHI	Overcooling Heat Index, (CHI - HI) , °C
ECW	thermal energy for cooling and condense, kWh th/y
ΔE%	overcooling energy, the ratio of actual energy consumption to baseline in CHI and OCAC, %
hrC	actual cooling hours, hr/y
Δhr%	overcooling hours, the ratio of actual cooling hours (hrC) to comfort hours' baseline in CHI and OCAC (hrCHI), %

Table 6 - Overcooling Heat Index (OCHI), energy consumption (ECW), and cooling hours (hrC) – Tel Aviv

Cool On °C	AveHICdn °C	OCHI °C	ECW kWh	ΔE%	hrC hr/y	Δhr%
16	15.44	11.16	12,200	206%	6,703	153%
17	16.54	10.06	11,337	184%	6,307	138%
18	17.64	8.96	10,461	162%	5,895	123%
19	18.75	7.85	9,574	140%	5,444	106%
20	19.85	6.75	8,713	118%	5,017	90%
21	20.96	5.64	7,865	97%	4,599	74%
22	22.06	4.54	7,007	76%	4,177	58%
23	23.16	3.44	6,139	54%	3,749	42%
24	24.26	2.34	5,309	33%	3,340	26%
25	25.35	1.25	4,497	13%	2,927	11%
OCAC						
25.6	26.01	0.59	3,990	0%	2,647	0%
Baseline	26.60	0.00	3,990		2,647	

Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning - OverAC

The Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC) determine the comfort conditions of cooling.

Usually, the air conditioning systems are set to a much lower temperature than CHI or OCAC, resulting in overcooling.

As mentioned before, cooling below the Comfort Heat Index not only wastes energy but also causes serious discomfort and health hazards to many people.

Lowering the air conditioning temperature below the Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC) and below the Comfortable Heat Index (CHI) has a twofold impact on air conditioning discomfort: lower temperature and more cooling hours.

In this work, Heat Index above or below the Comfort Heat Index is equally regarded as discomfort conditions.

Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning (OverAC) has two components:

- OCHI - difference between the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and the actual Heat Index (HI)
- Extended period of cooling with overcooling

Formula 2 - Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning (OverAC)

$$\text{OverAC} = \text{OCHI} * \Delta hr$$

$$\Delta hr = hrC - hrCHI$$

<i>OverAC</i>	Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning, dhr (degree-hours)
<i>dhr</i>	degree-hours, unit of OverAC
<i>CHI</i>	Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C
<i>AveHICdn</i>	average Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours, °C
<i>Δhr</i>	overcooling hours, difference between actual cooling hours and comfort hours at CHI level, hr/y
<i>hrC</i>	actual cooling hours, hr/y
<i>hrCHI</i>	cooling hours at CHI level, hr/y

Determination of Baseline Data for OverAC

The baseline data are for Comfort Heat Index (CHI), 26.6°C.

The source of data is the BESOO simulation programs. The BESOO programs calculate OCHI but cannot calculate cooling hours at CHI. Therefore, the baseline cooling hours are determined at OCAC temperatures. This approach is conservative as the OCAC average Heat Index is lower than the Comfort Heat Index.

Table 7 - Determination of OverAC baseline

		Jerusalem	Tel Aviv
OCAC	°C	25.4	25.6
Cooling period at OCAC	hr/y	1,016	2,647
Comfort Heat Index (CHI)	°C	26.6	26.6
Baseline cooling period	hr/y	1,016	2,647

Table 8 - OverAC baseline for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

		Jerusalem	Tel Aviv
Baseline Heat Index	°C	26.6	26.6
Baseline cooling period	hr/y	1,016	2,647

Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning (OverAC) for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

Table 9 - OverAC in range 25.4°C-16°C in Jerusalem

Cool On °C	AveHICdn °C	OCHI °C	hrC hr	Δhr hr	OverAC dhr
16	15.06	11.54	5,473	4,457	51,434
17	16.16	10.44	5,081	4,065	42,439
18	17.24	9.36	4,689	3,673	34,379
19	18.32	8.28	4,256	3,240	26,827
20	19.38	7.22	3,800	2,784	20,100
21	20.42	6.18	3,276	2,260	13,967
22	21.46	5.14	2,702	1,686	8,666
23	22.51	4.09	2,124	1,108	4,532
24	23.56	3.04	1,632	616	1,873
25	24.61	1.99	1,178	162	322
OCAC					
25.4	25.02	1.58	1,016	0	0
Baseline	26.60	0.00	1,016	0	0

Table 10 - OverAC in range 25.6°C-16°C in Tel Aviv

Cool On °C	AveHICdn °C	OCHI °C	hrC hr	Δhr hr	OverAC dhr
16	15.44	11.16	6,703	4,056	45,265
17	16.54	10.06	6,307	3,660	36,820
18	17.64	8.96	5,895	3,248	29,102
19	18.75	7.85	5,444	2,797	21,956
20	19.85	6.75	5,017	2,370	15,998
21	20.96	5.64	4,599	1,952	11,009
22	22.06	4.54	4,177	1,530	6,946
23	23.16	3.44	3,749	1,102	3,791
24	24.26	2.34	3,340	693	1,622
25	25.35	1.25	2,927	280	350
OCAC					
25.6	26.01	0.59	2,647	0	0
Baseline	26.60	0.00	2,647	0	0

OverAC and Waste of Energy

Chart 2 - OverAC and waste of energy - Jerusalem

Chart 3 - OverAC and waste of energy – Tel Aviv

BESOO Website

The BESOO Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization programs used for this work are available (free, no need to login) on:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

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